

Title: Home Automation and Optimizations

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INTRODUCTION:

Optimizations in IoT devices as the devices number gets larger. Storage of this data with ease of access and taking less space.

AIM:

To reduce time series data which in return reduces the storage required and sending messages to IoT devices faster and efficiently.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

In the app of the consumer store the IP Address and the SSID of each device he/she owns. If the owner sends the message to the device and the owner is connected to the same network then send the data through local network. This will result in no lag communication. For time series data storage, send only to the server the data which is changing. If the data is not changing, and if the device is connected, store the amount of time the data didn't change.

RESULTS:

Depending on your data change rate and use case, this could save lots of storage. E.g. if your data did not change for 1 hour and you didn't deploy this structure, you could be storing let's say 1 GB. If you did deploy this structure, you could save 1 GB and store this in bytes.

CONCLUSIONS:

Instant communication with device if on same network. Saves cost for storage.

KEYWORDS:

IoT, Full Stack Solutions, Optimizations

BIOGRAPHY:

Haris Barki studied 2 years at University of Saskatchewan and 2 years at Memorial University of Newfoundland. He has been actively pursuing Computer Science and the modern technologies. He has worked as Full Stack Developer at Celestica and is Co-founder of 2 companies. Audome is the IoT company for Home Automation and Event Ryno is attendee engagement platform. Both companies are still in development.